

4-Thiazolidinones, Part XXIV. 5-(2-oxo-3-Indolinylidene)-3-Aryl-2-Phenylimino-4-Thiazolidinones from new mixed 4-Thiazolidinones

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CONDENSATIONS of 4-thiazolidinones with isatin has been reported to yield thioindigoid dyes^{1,2}. We wish to report similar condensation of mixed 4-thiazolidinones with isatin to give 5-(2-oxo-3-indolinylidene)-3-aryl-2-phenylimino-4-thiazolidinones (I). The i.r. spectra of several of these thioindigoid dyes were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer model 337

The 3-aryl-2-phenylimino-4-thiazolidinones required for the synthesis of the thioindigoid dyes, were all prepared by standard literature methods^{3,4}. The data characterizing the synthesised compounds are summarized in Table 2. A typical experiment with details of preparation is described below :

5-(2-Oxo-3-indolinylidene)-3-o-chlorophenyl-2-phenylimino-4-thiazolidinone : 3-o-Chlorophenyl-2-phenylimino-4-thiazolidinone (5 g., 0.016 mole), isatin (2.1 g., 0.015 mole), fused anhydrous sodium acetate (3.5 g., 0.04 mole) and absolute ethanol (50 ml.) were refluxed for 3 hr. At the start of the reaction, the solids went into solution and a dark red precipitate appeared during the progress of the reaction. At the end, the reaction mixture was poured into 400 ml. of water and the brownish red precipitate, which separated was filtered, washed successively with water, ethanol (10 ml.) and carbon tetrachloride (15 ml.)

TABLE 1. I.R. ABSORPTION OF SOME THIOINDIGOID DYES

S.No.	Compounds (I) (Aryl group, Ar)	Intensity range cm. ⁻¹					S
		NH	CO	C = C	C = N	Monosubstituted phenyl	
1.	<i>o</i> Chlorophenyl	3200	1710	1660	1615	1495, 1475, 792, 694	752
2.	<i>p</i> Iodophenyl	3200	1710	1640	1600	1495, 1470, 794, 696	752
3.	<i>p</i> -Hydroxyphenyl*	3200	1700	1630	1600	1510, 1475, 796, 698	756
4.	2,5-Dichlorophenyl	3200	1700	1660	1620	1595, 1460, 796, 694	756
5.	Benzyl**	3220	1710	1690	1625	1495, 1470, 795, 700	754

* The hydroxy group is suggested by a peak at 3350 cm.⁻¹.
** A band at 3010 cm.⁻¹ shows a CH₂ group.

TABLE 2. 5-(2-OXO-3-INDOLINYLIDENE)-3-ARYL-2-PHENYLIMINO-4-THIAZOLIDINONES*

S.No.	Ar group	M.P. °C	Yield %	Colour	Colour in Conc. H ₂ SO ₄	Molecular Formula
1.	<i>o</i> -Chlorophenyl	above 250	60	Red	Dark red	C ₂₃ H ₁₄ ClN ₃ O ₂ S
2.	<i>m</i> -Chlorophenyl	"	57	Orange red	Orange red	"
3.	<i>p</i> -Chlorophenyl	"	65	Deep red	Dark red	"
4.	<i>p</i> -Bromophenyl	"	43	Yellowish red	Orange red	C ₂₃ H ₁₄ BrN ₃ O ₂ S
5.	<i>p</i> -Iodophenyl	"	62	Violet red	Violet	C ₂₃ H ₁₁ IN ₃ O ₂ S
6.	<i>m</i> -Hydroxyphenyl	"	57	Orange red	Deep red	C ₂₃ H ₁₅ N ₃ O ₃ S
7.	<i>p</i> -Hydroxyphenyl	"	62	Red	Dark red	"
8.	2,4-Dichlorophenyl	241	60	Orange red	Red	C ₂₃ H ₁₃ Cl ₂ N ₃ O ₂ S
9.	2,5-Dichlorophenyl	235	50	Deep red	Dark red	"
10.	Benzyl	221	63	Red	Dark red	C ₂₄ H ₁₇ N ₃ O ₂ S

* All the compounds gave good analytical data for C, H and N in good agreement with the molecular formulae.

infracord in the form of KBr-discs. An account of the band maxima in cm.⁻¹ for some compounds studied has been given in Table 1.

and dried, to give the title compound as a red woolly crystalline mass, which dissolved in concentrated sulphuric acid to give a dark red solution. Yield, 3.7 g. (60%); m.p. > 250°.

References

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